

The total value of loans granted by microfinance as a percentage of GDP at the global level

The variable "Microfinance gross loans, % GDP" represents the total value of loans granted by microfinance institutions (MFIs) as a percentage of a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Microfinance is a financial system that provides credit, savings, insurance, and other financial products to people who have limited or no access to traditional banking services, often because they live in poverty or operate within the informal economy. This variable expresses the importance and impact of the microfinance sector in relation to the national economy. Calculating gross loans as a percentage of GDP allows us to understand how much the microfinance sector contributes to or interacts with the overall economic fabric of a country. If this percentage is high, it may indicate that a significant portion of the population and small businesses rely on microfinance services, highlighting the sector's importance for financial inclusion and economic development. On the other hand, a low percentage may indicate that the sector is still limited or that other forms of financing are prevalent. Microfinance plays a crucial role in developing countries, where traditional banks may not be able to serve low-income communities. Through microcredit, individuals can access capital to start small businesses, improve their housing conditions, or address financial emergencies. Therefore, monitoring the gross loans of MFIs as a percentage of GDP provides a key indicator of the penetration and effectiveness of financial inclusion policies. However, if the level of microcredit is excessively high compared to GDP, it could also signal a fragile economy, where small businesses and informal workers make up too large a portion of overall economic activity. The data is available for the period 2013-2021.

Total value of microfinance loans as a percentage of GDP in 2021. The data on the total value of microfinance loans as a percentage of GDP in 2021 shows notable variability across countries, highlighting the differing importance of the microfinance sector in various economies. It is evident that the microfinance sector plays a significant role in many developing economies, with some nations showing extremely high percentages, up to 100% of GDP. Analyzing this data allows for several conclusions and observations. Bolivia, Ecuador, Cambodia, Mongolia, Peru, Rwanda, and Tajikistan all report a percentage of 100%. This figure can be interpreted in various ways. On one hand, it could indicate a strong penetration of microfinance and a great success of financial inclusion policies in these countries. In such economies, many people, especially in rural or marginalized areas, may rely on microfinance as their main source of credit, given the limited availability of traditional banking services. On the other hand, such a high percentage could also be a signal of economic vulnerability: if the microfinance sector represents the entire value of GDP, it means a significant portion of the economy depends on small loans, often with high interest rates, which could increase the risks of over-indebtedness. Paraguay (76.7%), Kyrgyzstan (75.8%), Kenya (74.4%), and Vietnam (55.4%) follow with similarly significant percentages, although they do not reach 100%. In these countries, microfinance is clearly a crucial pillar of the economy, providing support to small entrepreneurs, farmers, and informal workers. However, it is crucial to note that such high percentages, even if below 100%, raise similar concerns to those in countries with maximum percentages: these markets could be saturated or excessively dependent on microfinance credit, with potential economic instability risks if credit conditions or interest rates were to change rapidly. Countries like Togo (35.3%), Azerbaijan (33.1%), and Colombia (32.2%) fall within this range. These countries show a significant presence of the microfinance sector, but not as dominant as in the previous cases. A percentage between 10% and 50% indicates a balance between microfinance and other credit channels,

suggesting a more diversified financial ecosystem. However, a strong reliance on microfinance might still indicate that traditional banking services are not yet fully accessible to all segments of the population. Countries such as Tunisia (9.1%), Sri Lanka (9%), and Malawi (8.7%) fall into the lower range, where the contribution of microfinance relative to GDP is limited. In these contexts, it is likely that access to formal credit and traditional banking services is more widespread, or that the microfinance sector is not yet fully developed. This could present an opportunity for sector growth, especially if microcredit is promoted as a tool for economic development and financial inclusion. Many countries, including Egypt (1.3%), Brazil (2%), and South Africa (0.2%), show very low values. In these economies, microfinance plays a limited role, likely due to a well-developed formal banking sector capable of reaching even the lower-income segments of the population. However, a low value could also indicate a lack of development in the microfinance sector, which might still be in a growth phase or is not incentivized politically and economically. The data highlights a wide diversity in the role of microfinance in global economies. While it serves as a primary credit source in some countries, in others it plays a marginal role. It is crucial to consider these differences within the context of economic and social development, as access to credit is a key element for promoting inclusive growth and reducing poverty. However, excessive reliance on microfinance can also signal risks of instability and over-indebtedness, requiring careful monitoring and appropriate policies to balance credit access with economic sustainability."

Total value of microfinance loans as a percentage of GDP from 2013 to 2021. The data on the "Total value of microfinance loans as a percentage of GDP" from 2013 to 2021 shows very different trends across various countries, indicating a variety of economic dynamics, financial development, and socio-economic conditions. The analysis can be divided into three main groups: countries with significant growth, countries with minimal or stable variations, and countries with a drastic reduction in the incidence of microfinance. Some countries have seen an exponential increase in the incidence of microfinance relative to GDP, such as Rwanda (+1349.28%), Panama (+825%), and Poland (+566.67%). This growth indicates a significant expansion of access to microfinance services, likely supported by government policies or an increase in the demand for financial services by small businesses and individuals who were previously excluded from the traditional banking system. Rwanda, in particular, demonstrates how microcredit can become a crucial element in the economy of a developing country, promoting financial inclusion and the development of micro and small enterprises. In countries like India (+514.81%) and Madagascar (+184.62%), the increase in the value of loans granted by microfinance may reflect both an improvement in microcredit structures and a rise in confidence in the services offered by microfinance institutions. These figures also suggest that financial inclusion continues to be a central goal in many emerging economies. Some countries like Angola, Bolivia, Cambodia, and Tajikistan have maintained a consistent value of microfinance as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2021. This could indicate a stabilization of the microfinance sector, where economic growth and the supply of microcredit have balanced each other. In other words, the use of microcredit might already be consolidated and represents a stable component of the economy, with no significant changes, either positive or negative. In other cases, the incidence of microcredit on GDP has decreased dramatically. Countries such as Armenia (-86.72%), Albania (-89.35%), and South Africa (-97.06%) have seen a marked reduction in the loans granted. This phenomenon could be due to various factors, such as economic contraction, political instability, or a shift in microfinance policies that reduced access to or demand for such services. For example, in South Africa and other countries, the decrease could indicate that, although microfinance was initially an important resource for financial inclusion, other forms of financing have emerged over time, or the sector has faced stricter regulations. Countries like Ethiopia (-97.97%) and Indonesia (-97.67%) may have experienced economic difficulties, which reduced people's ability to access microloans or

forced institutions to cut back on loan offerings. In some cases, the decrease might also reflect a transition towards more structured or regulated financial systems that have supplanted the use of microcredit. The data shows that the evolution of microfinance is highly variable and depends on local factors, including economic policies, the development of financial infrastructures, and socio-economic conditions. The exponential growth in some countries highlights the potential of microcredit as a tool for financial inclusion, while the decrease in others suggests that this sector can be vulnerable to economic and political changes. To better interpret these data, it would be useful to also analyze other economic and social indicators that influence access to financial services in each country.

Conclusions. The total value of microfinance loans as a percentage of GDP between 2013 and 2021 increased from 22.05 units to 22.19 units, representing an increase of +0.14 units or +0.64%. The top-performing countries are Rwanda with +1349.28%, Panama with +825.00%, Poland with +566.67%, India with +514.81%, and Zambia with +500.00%. The worst-performing countries are Romania with -94.74%, Tanzania with -94.80%, South Africa with -97.06%, Indonesia with -97.67%, and Ethiopia with -97.97%.

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	Country	2013	2021	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performers	Rwanda	6,9	100	93,1	1349,28
	Panama	0,8	7,4	6,6	825,00
	Poland	0,3	2	1,7	566,67
	India	2,7	16,6	13,9	514,81
	Zambia	0,2	1,2	1	500,00
Worse Performers	Romania	1,9	0,1	-1,8	-94,74
	Tanzania	44,2	2,3	-41,9	-94,80
	South Africa	6,8	0,2	-6,6	-97,06
	Indonesia	12,9	0,3	-12,6	-97,67
	Ethiopia	14,8	0,3	-14,5	-97,97

